

What Remains of the Link between Food and Spirituality in Postmodern Societies?¹

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I would like to propose that we discuss the following question: *What remains of the link between food and spirituality in postmodern societies?* By *postmodern*, I mean a form of disenchantment with modernity in light of past hopes, born with the Enlightenment and carried forward by capitalism, whose effects are realised in the fragmentation of both the individual and time.

My argument will consist of three parts. In the first, I will revisit several foundational elements to shed light on this issue from an anthropological perspective. I will recall what Claude Lévi-Strauss considers to be the boundary between nature and culture. I shall address the notion of incorporation to understand what eating means. Finally, I shall distinguish the sacred from the spiritual.

In the second part, I shall approach the contemporary determinants of the breakdown, unravelling the link between spirituality and food through changes in space–place and space–time. Finally, in the third part, I shall evoke the partial reconstructions of these links through certain currents within new eating habits.

Numerous works by historians and anthropologists attest to the ancestral connections that human beings have woven between food, the sacred, and spirituality. It would be futile, indeed impossible, to list them all, and I will not attempt to do so. Nevertheless, I would like to mention a few key points for the purposes of my argument.

¹ The original title of the French paper is: *Que reste-t-il du lien entre alimentation et spiritualité dans les sociétés post-modernes?*

To address the relationship between food, the sacred, and the spiritual, we must first establish that, for human beings, eating is not merely the satisfaction of a purely physiological need; instead, this act is subverted by the psyche, which inscribes it as a cultural fact. Claude Lévi-Strauss substantiated this viewpoint at length in *The Raw and the Cooked*.² He suggests that cooking is a symbol of the transition from nature to culture: animals, after all, do not cook their food. For Lévi-Strauss, cooking lies at the origin of cuisine, that is, the transformation of food for taste or digestibility. Even if the digestibility of food is a physiological matter, taking an interest in it entails intentionality: transforming food from one state to another to promote well-being and digestive comfort.

Moreover, Lévi-Strauss considers that cooking, through human fire and as the passage from nature to culture, resolves the anguished tension of the myth of the relationship between heaven and earth, a myth in which two opposing situations confront one another. On the one hand, a sun too close to the Earth could heat food, but at the risk of burning the entire world if it drew any closer. On the other hand, a sun too far from the Earth would plunge it into a long night, giving rise to a world that he describes as rotten.

Based on Claude Lévi-Strauss's conclusion that cooking is a cultural phenomenon, we find ourselves at a loss when it comes to defining what might count as natural versus cultural food absorption. That is to say, how can we distinguish, through a verb, the natural from the cultural fact? Which verb should we choose among *to feed oneself*, *to nourish oneself*, *to eat*, *to absorb*, *to consume*, *to sustain oneself*, and so forth?

If we cannot rely upon a distinctive use of a verb to enable us to separate the natural from the cultural, I suggest that we do so by considering the existence of intentionality in action. The sensation of hunger conditions the search for food. There are many biological determinants of this sensation, many of which are hormonal. Even if this sensation exists in human beings, it is usually not the direct cause of food intake. We eat because it is the appropriate time, because it is our break at work, because we are bored, or because we have been invited to a friend's house, and so on. We may be hungry and not eat, or we may eat without being hungry. In these circumstances, eating is no longer the result of hunger alone; it has become a social and cultural fact linked to intentionality. Even the urge to eat is an unconscious intentionality that performs a function

² Claude Lévi-Strauss, *The Raw and the Cooked: Mythologiques*, vol. 1 (Chicago: Chicago University Press, 1983).

within the subject's psychological economy. In these circumstances, there is a dissociation between nature, a response to the sensation of hunger, and culture, the moment when we eat.

How, then, can we draw this semantic distinction? Through intentionality, as we have just seen, but I also suggest starting not from the consequence, that is, feeding ourselves, but from the cause, that is, why do we eat? This allows us to distinguish the sensation of hunger, as the only determinant that would fall within our nature, from the many other determinants that would lead us, in this case, to consider the act of eating as a cultural fact. That is why I shall employ the verbs mentioned above without any fundamental distinction to refer to the consequence: eating. At the end of this inquiry, we can be certain that while eating is a natural act in terms of our biological needs, it is also, and perhaps even more so, a cultural fact integrated into an interactionist social space, and therefore belongs to the symbolic. It is precisely within this space of meaning that we may address our initial question about the link between spirituality and food.

The second point to which I would like to draw your attention, and which follows directly from what I have just said, is that eating refers to the principle of incorporation. Borrowed from Ludwig Feuerbach, the expression "*Der Mensch ist was er ißt*" (or "people are what they eat")³ captures the cultural, social, and psychological dimensions of food within the process of identity construction remarkably well. What, then, does it mean to eat? According to the psycho-sociologist Christine Durif-Bruckert (Durif-Bruckert, 2016), it consists, if I may quote her, "in taking objects from outside and placing them inside our body, making them cross bodily boundaries, the limits of the body, and transporting them into one's personal sphere." If we refer to David Le Breton: "the body is the instance of separation (boundary)."⁴ He continues: "Thus, the external objects that food constitutes 'in itself' become internal objects, that is, food 'for oneself,' by virtue of this breaching of a barrier that is both real and symbolic." It is through this process of appropriation – through the principle of incorporation – that the symbolic, meaning itself, emerges. Finally, as the sociologist Claude Fischler observes: "Food constitutes the royal road to accessing manifestations of magical thinking. This is because our relationship with food touches, within

3 Ludwig Feuerbach, *L'homme est ce qu'il mange – Le mystère du sacrifice*, (Paris: Poche, 2008).

4 David Le Breton, *Anthropologie du corps et modernité* (Paris: Presses Universitaires de France, Quadrige, 2010), 47.

us, what is the most intimate part of ourselves, in the etymological sense of the term: *intimus*, in Latin, is the superlative of *interior*.”⁵ Food thus becomes a part of oneself.

To conclude this first part, I would like to address what we mean when we speak of spirituality. We must dissociate the notion of the sacred from that of spirituality, for while one may find spirituality within the sacred, the converse is not true. There exists a secular spirituality which may be thought of as a set of symbolic links that transform the very nature of an object – in this case, food – into a meaningful element, that is, one that takes on an entirely different value in the eyes of the person who consumes it. This process of shifting meaning is particularly striking when it comes to the sacred. This is the case with the mystery of the Eucharist: what is bread and wine becomes the body and blood of Christ. The mystery transforms two secular objects, two common foods, into something sacred, in remembrance of the Last Supper, “the source and summit of all Christian life,” according to Vatican II.⁶ The Eucharist is perhaps the quintessence of the sacred when viewed through the principle of incorporation.

In a similar vein, cannibalism also proceeds from a powerful symbolic incorporation that goes beyond the spiritual dimension of the meal alone. It is not a matter of consuming food, but of consuming the signifier, the symbolic that becomes flesh. The appropriation of the enemy’s warrior virtues takes place through the incorporation of his very body. This ritual finds expression through and within the ritualised space of the meal. In a more ordinary meal, which nevertheless remains a ritual, the principle of incorporation is still at work, but to a lesser degree, setting aside its religious value in favour of its magical representation.

Now that we have distinguished the sacred from the spiritual, established the principle of incorporation as a signifier that bears meaning, and combined symbolism, intertwined symbol and necessity, in the act of feeding and nourishing ourselves, I will draw upon the ritualised dimension of the meal to address the second part of my argument, which concerns, in the strict sense, what remains of the link between spirituality and food in our societies.

5 Claude Fischler, “Magie, charmes et aliments,” in *Manger magique: Aliments, sorciers, croyances comestibles*, Autrement, série Mutations/Mangeurs, no. 149 (Novembre 1994), 10.

6 Second Vatican Council, *Sacrosanctum Concilium* (Constitution on the Sacred Liturgy), 1963, sec. 2; Second Vatican Council, *Lumen Gentium* (Dogmatic Constitution on the Church), 1964, sec. 11.

I believe that there is a partial blurring between secular and profane spirituality and food in postmodern societies due to the relative destructuring of the meal. This operates across multiple dimensions of space and time. Without claiming to be exhaustive, I shall address the relationship between space and time through the notions of space-place and space-time in social interaction processes. The meal, as the most ritualised manifestation of food intake, will serve as both the framework and the guide for my argument.

Until quite recently, no more than a few decades ago, meals were supposed to take place in a space-place assigned to a specific function. While restaurants remain this designated place within public spaces, what about dining rooms within private spaces? Architectural reconfigurations of modern apartments and houses tend to merge three living spaces: the open-plan kitchen, the sitting room and the dining room, often referred to as the living room or the main living area. This rearrangement is not insignificant in relation to our question, since the designation of the “dining room” is dissolving into functions other than eating, and is also disappearing from language. Even if the table and chairs continue to define a space dedicated to eating, it is no longer exclusive in its function. Moreover, meals may be eaten in the kitchen, at the living room table, or even in bed, depending on the circumstances. This disappearance contributes to the reduction of this space-place in its ritualised symbolic representation of the meal.

Gradually, other spaces-places have developed in urban centres, including the street. “Street food” in Western societies has altered the relationship to space through a public staging of the act of eating, which was long confined to the privacy and intimacy of the home. To conclude this discussion of space-place, let us allow ourselves a brief detour to Asia and the Middle East, where street cuisine continues to offer traditional, simple, and often tasty food in stalls open onto public spaces. At the end of this very brief global overview, we can observe that what characterises street food is not so much that it is an emerging phenomenon in public spaces, since it is ancestral, but rather the symbolic modifications that the modern eater has made in relation to food, modifications that are disrupting their relationship with food.

It is for this reason that I believe we must distinguish between “street food,” as a manifestation of postmodernity, and street cuisine, which is part of tradition; a distinction grounded not in its nourishing function (both provide this), but in its social roots. In the same way, it is not the gradual disappearance of the “dining room” space that is disrupting the modern eater’s relationship

with meals – other spaces are dedicated to this purpose – but rather the food choices, and the individuation of these choices in relation to the group.

Consequently, whether on the street or at home, the relationship between spirituality and food is changing. By way of illustration, a 2022 Italian study highlights that, while the division into three meals remains customary in Italy, there is today a gradual shift away from Mediterranean cuisine in favour of a more energy-intensive diet with a higher carbon footprint, based on a globalised food model.⁷ It is as if there were an erosion of identity regarding the symbolic value of food. This observation is not a matter of nostalgia: societies have always benefited from the mixing of cuisines. What is occurring is the deletion of cultural anchoring, which undermines the very recognition of the foods consumed, since they can no longer be linked to memories of taste, ambience, or affective ties.

Having observed the transformation of space-place, let us now turn to the notion of space-time, which we touched upon earlier through the concept of meal distribution. We observe that in Southern Europe, the time devoted to meals remains significant. By way of example, every ten years in France, the National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies publishes the results of a survey on the eating habits of the French population. For several decades now, the results have remained stable: the French people spend nearly two and a half hours a day at the table, eat three distinct meals, and prefer to eat at home. This three-meal pattern is found in most European countries. In comparison, in the United States, the three meals are less clearly delineated, and food intake throughout the day is interspersed with snacks.

Moreover, and contrary to widespread assumptions, most European and North American populations prefer to eat at home, as evidenced by a decline in restaurant attendance in the United States in recent years. The effects of the Covid-19 crisis undoubtedly played a role in this trend, but they do not account for it entirely. In his book *Alienation and Acceleration: Towards a Critical Theory of Late Modernity*,⁸ Hartmut Rosa invites us to reflect on the fact “that one way

7 Giuliana Vinci et al, “A Comparison of the Mediterranean Diet and Current Food Patterns in Italy: A Life Cycle Thinking Approach for Sustainable Consumption,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, no. 19 (2022): 12274.

8 Hartmut Rosa, *Aliénation et accélération: Vers une théorie critique de la modernité tardive*. Translated by Thomas Chaumont. (Paris: La Découverte, 2012), 8. Id. *Alienation and Acceleration: Towards a critical Theory of Late Modern Temporality*. (Copenhagen: Nordic Summer University Press, 2010).

of examining the structure and quality of our lives is to focus on temporal patterns. It is not only that almost all aspects of life can be approached in an illuminating way from a temporal perspective, but also that temporal structures reflect both the microscopic and macroscopic levels of society, that is to say, our actions and orientations are coordinated and rendered compatible with the ‘systemic imperatives’ of modern capitalist societies through temporal norms, constraints, and regulations.”

If, according to the studies cited, the time devoted to eating has not been profoundly altered in postmodern societies, it is because, as Hartmut Rosa argues, there exist “oases of deceleration”: genuine islands of resistance, albeit ones that remain subject to the erosion of the dominant temporal dynamic. Meals may thus be understood as a form of cultural inertia rather than the result of a conscious choice, even though certain movements seek to reaffirm the meal’s structuring role as a temporal break. The expression “meal break” itself conveys something of this interruption of time. We are aware, however, that the phenomenon of temporal acceleration is not entirely foreign to street food, if only through the very term designating its preferred site of consumption – “fast food” – which clearly signals its rupture with traditional temporality.

Thus, if space-place is altered by the gradual disappearance of the dining room, albeit with substitute spaces, and if the space-time devoted to meals still frequently constitutes an oasis of deceleration, how, then, is the link between food and spirituality affected?

It is on the side of street food, understood as the archetype of urban nourishment, that we may identify certain elements of an answer. Street food confronts us with two essential issues: the symbolic dimension of the food consumed, and the effects on social interactions during the meal. As I stated at the outset of my presentation, food is always a cultural object, whether it takes the form of a slice of pizza or a burger. While the former connects us to Naples, and more broadly to Italy, the latter puts us in tune with North American culture. From the standpoint of pleasure, either one may be a source of satisfaction for the eater. It is therefore not in terms of satisfaction that we should seek our answer.

What has changed profoundly with street food is that it has sidelined language. In a sense, food is no longer spoken about; it becomes a solitary pleasure, generating distant forms of social interactions. The eater is lost between anonymity and curiosity about others, becoming the object of glances rather than of exchanges. I suggested at the beginning that, in the act of eating,

the food ingested relates as much to energy as to symbolism. The erosion of the link between food and spirituality lies in the very nature of the food consumed, in the way it is eaten, and in the environment in which it is eaten.

The globalisation of food models is leading to a loss of meaning. The gradual loss of the food's cultural roots is distorting the meal's symbolic dimension and stripping it of its profane spiritual density. Food once again becomes a simple source of energy, breaking the chain of cultural meaning, even though, as I have already noted, the eater may still derive pleasure from consuming it. Along similar lines, the consumption of ultra-processed products distances the modern eater from any representations they may have of the food components of their meal. In both cases, globalised street food and ultra-processed foods, there is a loss of meaning that denatures, or one might say, deculturates, the meal.

Added to this phenomenon of symbolic loss is a marked shift towards the individualisation of food intake. The latter is clearly observable in street food, as pointed out earlier. The modalities of such meals – eaten standing up, or even while walking – operate at the expense of language. Food is no longer talked about; it escapes compliments and valuation/appreciation for what is being eaten, and detaches itself from the verbalised social fabric of the traditional meal. This is often compounded by compulsive screen consultation, which further distances the link of meaning between the food being eaten and the eater. The pavements of metropolitan cities thus become the privileged sites of mandibular wanderings, enclosed within a digital soundscape.

The individualisation of meal composition is not unique to street food. Home delivery services also contribute to the shift away from sharing a single dish among diners toward individual orders. The meal becomes a juxtaposition of eaters who share a space-place and a space-time, but no longer share a common food. How, then, are we to speak about these individualised forms of nourishment? As Claude Fischler writes with regard to magical eating: “When we say ‘you must have eaten lion this morning,’ to someone who is showing particular energy, it is a way of speaking. But it is also a way of thinking.”⁹ What, then, is the value of the externalised preparation of the meal, which removes any form of preparing food for others? All of these new forms of ready-to-eat meals bring us back to the concept of convenience, understood as a means of saving time, labour, or personal commitment, in the hope of investing these

9 Fischler, “Magie, charmes et aliments,” 10.

resources elsewhere. The standardisation of eating habits fits perfectly with the logic of convenience in terms of social productivity.

Admittedly, as we have seen, alternative and countervailing movements within these oases of resistance slow the overall dynamic of this system. This observation leads me to my third point.

I shall attempt to shed light on new forms of food choices that have emerged in response to this de-structuring of meals, marked by the abandonment of shared dishes in favour of individualised choices served in disposable containers. To this must be added the spread of the stereotypical globalised food model. It would, however, be wrong to view this as a single, homogeneous current – a veritable tsunami of standardised food practices devoid of discernment. Several recent trends invite us to reconsider our relationship with food.

The first of these promotes organic food. I do not seek here to assess the scientific legitimacy of eating organic here; rather, I am only interested in what the organic approach implies in terms of the relationship with nature and to health. The spiritual dimension of organic eating evokes a strong and powerful representation of health-conscious consumption, coupled with an environmental ethic. Two moral virtues are thus intertwined: caring for oneself and caring for the environment. This approach expresses a desire to reconcile the micro dimension (the self) with the macro dimension (the collective), within a perspective that seeks to respect both.

Two other major movements place the human being at the centre of representations of nature: vegetarianism and veganism, on the one hand, and rituals of bodily purification, on the other, which advocate the urgent need to rid the body of all forms of impurity, of which food is seen as a harmful/pernicious agent. In veganism, environmental concerns lie at the heart of a redefinition of the relationship that human beings must maintain with the rest of nature. The balance between food as a fact of nature and as a fact of culture is expressed through a confrontation between the living and the dead. Meat, understood as dead flesh, as cadaverous flesh, occupies a central place in this representation. The same logic also applies to processed products such as white sugar. A hierarchy of foods is thus established along two registers: a nutritional register, based on their composition and specific contributions, and a moral register, based on their environmental impact. It is through this latter dimension that we observe a revaluation of the link between spirituality and food.

As for the current movement that promotes the quest for an untainted body and bodily purification practices, it mobilises a different set of representations and cognitive frameworks. It rests on the principle that the body is threatened by all forms of incorporation. The passage from the exterior to the interior is perceived as potentially dangerous, given the need to maintain the body in a state akin to original purity. Much like the *pharmakon* – both a remedy and a poison – food itself carries within it an inherent potential to harm health. Prolonged fasting, water-based cleansing regimes, and various infusions are thus supposed to confer purifying effects upon the body. These trends draw on forms of magical thinking in service of the mind and healthy living. However, these new rituals raise questions about the place accorded to the body by their adherents. They recall Plato's assertion that "the body is the tomb of the soul,"¹⁰ as well as the Gnostic view that all matter, including the body, is evil.

At the conclusion of my presentation, what can we retain concerning what remains of the link between spirituality and food in postmodern societies? The de-structuring of meals and their increasing individualisation are among the major causes of the erosion of this link. Street food, which promotes standardised and globalised forms of eating, breaks with the cultural dimension that underpins the symbolic elaboration of food. It transforms both space–place and space–time, and fosters the disappearance of conversation: food is no longer spoken about. In response to this sociological observation, new food practices are emerging as forms of resistance. They emphasise a return to nature in highly diverse forms, ranging from environmental concerns to bodily purification rituals. We thus observe a tension between these different food practices, which clearly illustrates that eating is a complex act that generates a wide array of representations and, at the very least, cannot be reduced to the satisfaction of a purely organic need.

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10 Platon. *Le Cratyle* (Paris: GF, 1999).

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